

Homomorphic Free Energy Changes in Electron Transfer and Proton Transfer Tetrads

A. CHAKRAVORTY*

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032

The possible correlation of the formal potentials (E° 's) of an electron transfer agent displaying several (n) successive one-electron steps with logarithmic dissociation constants (pK 's) of a 'corresponding acid' having the same number (m , $m=n$) of successive one-proton dissociation is explored. Dithiolenes and dithiolene-like reagents ($n=4$) are used to illustrate the points; pyrophosphoric acid is chosen as the corresponding acid ($m=4$). The linear E° - pK correlation is utilised to estimate experimentally inaccessible redox potentials in dithiolenes.

THERE is a symbiotic relationship between electron transfer and proton transfer when these occur in the same molecule: electron addition favouring proton addition and *vice versa*^{1,2}. In this work, we explore the possible free energy correlation between electron transfer and proton transfer taking place in different molecules.

Results and Discussion

The concerned equilibria: In the elementary transfer processes (1) and (2), the free energy changes are respectively proportional to the standard

potential (E°) and the logarithmic dissociation constant (pK). We are concerned here with redox reagents which undergo several successive one-electron steps like (1) and acid-base reagents that display an equal number of successive one-proton steps of type (2). The purpose is to scrutinise whether the step by step free energy changes (E° 's) of the former correlate with those (pK 's) of the latter in a simple manner.

Redox reagents: the dithiolenes and related species: The complexes³⁻⁷ chosen here are the

well-studied bis-chelates of metal (II) ($M = Ni, Pd, Pt$) having the skeletal structure (1). They display

(1)

upto four exactly or nearly reversible couples (3)-(6) where each complex is simply identified by its charge (z) number⁸. In dithiolenes^{3,4}, only couples

(5) and (6) are experimentally observable. All the four couples are observed in some⁸ $MN_4^{(z)}$ and^{4,5} $MN_2S_2^{(z)}$ systems. Relevant data³⁻⁵ are collected in Table 1. All potentials are referenced to saturated calomel electrode.

TABLE 1—SELECTED E° AND ρ VALUES

Sl. no.	Compd.	E° (V) of couples				$-\rho$ (V)
		(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
1a	$Ni[S_2C_2(CF_3)_2]_2$	(3.2)	(2.8)	0.92	-0.12	0.40
1b	$Pd[S_2C_2(CF_3)_2]_2$	(2.9)	(2.5)	0.96	0.08	0.34
1c	$Pt[S_2C_2(CF_3)_2]_2$	(3.3)	(2.8)	0.82	-0.27	0.42
1d	$Ni[C_2H_4(NH)_2]_2$	0.73	0.14	-0.89	-1.43	0.25
1e	$Pd[C_2H_4(NH)_2]_2$	0.78	0.10	-0.89	-1.44	0.25
1f	$Pt[C_2H_4(NH)_2]_2$	0.78	0.23	-1.01	-1.70	0.29
1g	$Ni[PhNNO(NEt_3)S]_2$	0.71	0.51	-0.73	-1.06	0.22
1h	$Pt[PhNNO(NHBu(t)S)]_2$	0.84	0.49	-0.72	-1.23	0.25
1i	$Pt[PhNNO(NMe_3)S]_2$	0.80	0.44	-0.76	-1.19	0.25
1j	$Pt[PhNNO(NHPh)S]_2$	0.85	0.63	-0.50	-1.04	0.23

The corresponding acid : pyrophosphoric acid :
 We have to choose a tetrabasic acid whose proton dissociation equilibria might thermodynamically correlate with the above electron transfer equilibria (3)-(6) of **1**. Such an acid will be called the 'corresponding acid'. In **1**, there are two bidentate ligands bound at M as (XY)M(XY) and in all two-electrons are transferred per ligand. The corresponding acid chosen for **1** is pyrophosphoric acid (2). In this

acid each of the two oxophosphorous groups joined at the oxygen atom as $(O_3P)O(PO_3)$ can transfer two protons. The pK values⁸⁻¹⁰ of **2** are pK_1 , 0.9; pK_2 , 2.1; pK_3 , 6.7 and pK_4 , 9.3. In an electrostatic sense, the addition of an electron and the dissociation of a proton are analogous. The corresponding pairs are therefore: $E^0(3)$, pK_1 ; $E^0(4)$, pK_2 ; $E^0(5)$, pK_3 and $E^0(6)$, pK_4 whose $E^0(i)$ is the E^0 of couple (i).

The linear correlation : The plots of E^0 vs pK for $MN_4^{(z)}$ and $MN_2S_2^{(z)}$ species are presented in Fig. 1. A good straight line can be drawn for each individual $MX_2Y_2^{(z)}$ species and the slope (ρ) in each case is given in Table 1. In Fig. 1, however, only two straight lines have been drawn—one for the entire set of $MN_2^{(z)}$ species and one for all $MN_2S_2^{(z)}$ complexes. The significant point is that between **1** and **2**, E^0 and pK correlate linearly.

Fig. 1. Linear plot of the E^0 's of **1** and pK 's of **2**. The letter labels to points identify compounds of type **1** as in Table 1 (for brevity only the letter is retained e.g. Id is indicated simply as d). Solid lines represent least-square fits.

In **2**, the first and second (or third and fourth) proton dissociations occur from the coordination spheres of two different phosphorous atoms. Hence, the order $pK_1 < pK_2 \ll pK_3 < pK_4$. The successive addition of four electrons to **1** can be described by the simplified valence bond structural sequence (3) in which X, Y and substituents are not explicitly

shown. Electrons are considered to be transferred alternatively to the two chelate rings. This is a way of taking electron correlation into account. In couple (5) the electron is transferred for the first time to a ring which already has transferred an electron. We thus have the order $E^0(3) > E^0(4) \gg E^0(5) > E^0(6)$.

The similar bunching of pK 's and E^0 's is the crux of the observed correlation. The details of the forces involved in proton transfer and electron transfer are evidently different. Yet a correspondence can be established such that the gross thermodynamics of the two transfers assume a simple parallelism.

Other corresponding acids : While choosing **2** we considered a number of other tetrabasic acids. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid is a poor choice because of zwitterion formation and strong electrostatic interaction between closely spaced NH^+ centres. Its higher homologues¹¹ (where three or more carbon atoms intervene between the two

nitrogen atoms) are acceptable in as much as their pK 's correlate nearly linearly with pK 's of **2**. But there is no particular advantage in using one of these instead of **2**. A similar comment applies to the several diphosphonic acids¹¹ that could be chosen. The final choice of **2** is based on its molecular simplicity, its true H_4A nature (all protons equivalent to start with) and the $(O_3P)O(PO_3)$ and $(XY)M(XY)$ analogy.

The ρ parameter : The $(E^\circ - pK)$ linearity can be expressed as

$$\Delta E^\circ = \rho \Delta pK \quad (7)$$

where, ΔE° is the shift of E° between two couples, ΔpK is the corresponding shift in pK and ρ is the slope of the $(E^\circ - pK)$ line. In our treatment, ρ is intrinsically negative. The least-square values of ρ in cases where all four couples are known are in Table 1.

If it is assumed that $(E^\circ - pK)$ linearity also holds for dithiolenes, ρ can be calculated from the known values of $E^\circ(5)$ and $E^\circ(6)$ using equation (8) which readily follows from equation (7). The values of $E^\circ(3)$ and $E^\circ(4)$ can then be calculated from equations (9) and (10), respectively. Whereas such calculated values (given in parentheses in Table 1) are to be considered as rough estimates only, we nevertheless have a way of making such estimates.

$$\rho = 0.38[E^\circ(6) - E^\circ(5)] \quad (8)$$

$$E^\circ(3) = 0.5 [E^\circ(6) + E^\circ(5) - 14.2\rho] \quad (9)$$

$$E^\circ(4) = 0.5 [E^\circ(6) + E^\circ(5) - 11.8\rho] \quad (10)$$

It is seen that $E^\circ(3)$ and $E^\circ(4)$ are likely to occur at potentials that are too high for convenient experimental identification.

Concluding remarks : The fascinating correlation revealed in this work arises, as noted earlier, from the similar bunching of multiple E° 's and pK 's. It provides a useful tool for estimating inaccessible formal potentials of redox reagents. It could potentially be used for similar estimation of inaccessible pK values of corresponding acids. We have tested the applicability of the ideas developed above to a few cases other than (1). Hopefully many more examples will be found in due course.

Acknowledgement

Grants received from the Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged. The author thanks Dr. R. N. Mukherjee and Dr. P. Bandyopadhyay, for assistance.

References

1. A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Comments Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, **4**, 1.
2. P. GHOSH and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 2242.
3. J. A. MCCLEVERTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **10**, 49.
4. W. E. GEIGER, C. S. ALLEN, T. E. MINES and F. O. SENFTLEBER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 2003.
5. A. L. BALCH and R. H. HOLM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 5201.
6. C. E. FORBES, A. GOLD and R. H. HOLM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2479.
7. K. BECHGAARD, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1974, **28**, 185.
8. L. G. SILLEN and A. F. MARTELL, *Chem. Soc. Spec. Publ.*, 1971, 112.
9. L. G. SILLEN and A. F. MARTELL, *Chem. Soc. Spec. Publ.*, 1971, 306.
10. A. E. MARTELL and R. M. SMITH, "Critical Stability Constants", Plenum, New York, 1974, Vol. 4, p. 59.
11. Ref. 10, Vol. 1, p. 244.